

Children as an Important Actor in the Process of Family Purchase Decision for Food Products

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Abstract

Over the past two decades in Iran the effect of the children on consumer behavior has often been overlooked. However, consumer decision making within the family has begun to receive a growing amount of attention with the increased realisation of the magnitude of the children effect within the family as an important actor in purchasing decision making process. It can be said that in the past, role of the children in buying decision of families had been negligible. But due to development in digital media, children are the first to know about the products when they hit the market even before their parents. Nowadays, children act as an active participant in families buying decision. Children not only choose the products which belong to them but they also have upper hand on products which are used by almost every other family member.

This paper investigates the influence that children have on family consumer decision making. It takes the unique approach of investigating purchase influence from the perspective of both the child and the parent.

This paper aims to identify the most important influencing factors on children purchasing behavior in Iran. To this end, Bandar Abbas city has been selected for the study. The results of the study show that the most important variables to affect parental affiliation of children in the purchase decision are gender, age, pester power, TV advertising, peer group effects, household size, lesser time with family, income level, single parent households, more stress in life, culture, internet advertising, newspaper and magazine advertising, pocket money and mobile advertising.

Keywords: Children influence, Children purchasing decision, Parenting, Purchasing decision making

1. Introduction

Purchasing decision making is a complex and multistage process, which is undertaken not only by Purchaser himself, but under the influence of other parties as well (Thakur, 2014). The family has been identified as the most important decision making and consumption unit (Assael, 1998). Therefore the domain has attracted the interest of marketers and marketing academics over the years (e.g., Kim and Lee, 1997; Moore et al., 2002; Shoham & Dalakas, 2005).

The world belongs to kids. World has witnessed a tremendous change in past decades. Families are changing globally with a growing trend towards small and nuclear families. Iran has been part of these changes too. Iranian families have been previously characterized as Joint Families, however owing to many social, cultural and even economical reasons, the structure of Iranian families has changed to nuclear or small families. Exposure to globalized world and changing family profile has given a big push to Iranian Consumerism and today Iranian consumer is totally different from the previous ones, marketers are focusing on New Consumers – The Children.

Much research carried out on children's influence in family decision making emphasizes that children have at least some influence on decisions for a wide array of products and some even report that children have an increasing role in family purchase decisions (Ahuja et al., 1998; Atkin, 1978; Berkman et al., 1997; Bery & Pollay, 1968; Caruana & Vassallo, 2003; Chavda et al., 2005; Darley & Lim, 1986; Davis, 1976; Ferber, 1973; Isler et al., 1987; Jenkins, 1979; Mangleburg, 1990; McDonald, 1980; Miller et al. 1982; Nelson, 1978; Scanzoni, 1980; Swinyard & Sim, 1987; Szy-billo et al., 1977; Tufte, 2003; Ward & Wackman, 1972). Marketers today are targeting the children as their consumer because of two main reasons, first, both the discretionary income of children and their power to influence parent purchases have increased overtime, second as the enormous increase in the number of available Television channel has led to smaller audience for each channel, thereby creating a growing space just for children and children's products. Therefore, we can claim that kids have direct or indirect influence over family buying decisions. So this shows why it is important to study the role of children in family purchase decisions. As children's role in family decisions increases, so does the need for research that includes children (Foxman et al., 1989, p. 482).

The influence of children on the processes of family purchase decision depends on a number of parameters and situations. Children exercise various methods to influence their parent's decision to buy. This influence varies from one product to another and it depends on many factors (Kumar, 2013). This study attempts to identify and rank the most important factors in the intensity of children's influence on the family's decision-making process on buying food products as a major actor. To this end, families with children 6 to 12 years old have been selected in Bandar Abbas, Islamic Republic of Iran.

2. Literature Review

Despite an increase the spending power and actual purchases of children over the past few decades they have proven to be an elusive market for advertisers and marketers. They are the segment whose liking and disliking are most dynamic (Public Broadcasting Service). McNeal (1998) proposed in his research that as children finds security in attaching themselves with objects like pillow, blanket, brand, celebrity their curiosity has not yet been suppressed, so they do turn their attention to other objects, like other brands. A brand serves to add dimensions to a product to differentiate it in some way or other products designed to satisfy the same need. The strengths of the brand is measured by the price differential consumers are willing to pay over other products in the same category. Their research suggests that as early as six months of age, babies are forming mental images of corporate logos and mascots.

2.1 Children Socialization

The most widely used definition of consumer socialization is the one given by Ward: (Alder et al. 1997)

“It is the process by which young people acquire skills, knowledge and attitude relevant to their functioning in the marketplace”. (Kaur and Singh) children in family purchase decision.

Integrating Piaget’s stage theory of intellectual development and Selman’s stage theory of social development, John proposes a model of consumer socialization in which children learning consumers are theorized to undergo a developmental process in three stages. Its start from perceptual stage to analytical stage and followed by reflective stage. Parent role is considered to be most instrumental in teaching their children consumer behavior (Moore RL & Moschis GP, 1981; Mascarenhas OAJ & Higby MA, 1993)

Peers also have great effect on children socialization like parents. For the learning of the expressive elements of consumption in children peers play vital role as a socialization agent. Influence of the peers socialization increase with the age as the parental influence wanes (Alder et al. 1997). Children plays different role in the purchasing decision as it is stated in; children constitute three different markets: the primary, influencer, and the future market. Such products are simply children products for these product children play the primary role. For other products such as one used by entire family unit they may influence purchases made by the parents. For other products parents buying pattern are affected by the prior knowledge of the tastes and preferences of their children. It is also observed that children are socialize by their parents to act as rational consumers (Shahzad M, Rehman A, 2015). Influence of children varies by product, product subdecision, stage of the decision-making process, nature of socializing of the children, families, gender role, orientation, and demographic features such as age and gender and also by respondent selected for investigation of relative influence (Bachmann GR et al. 1993). After the parents, the resource that is considered to be the most effective socialization agent for the children is mass media (Moore RL & MoschisGP, 1981).

2.2 Children Influence in Family Decision Making

Examining the family decision making process, Szybillo and Sosanie (as cited in Shabbir MS, 2015) suggested that in all three decision stages (problem recognition, search for information and final selection) all members of family (husband, wife, and children) are greatly involved. Some other researcher purposed a research that children exert considerable influence while problem recognition and search stages and least influence while final decision making (Bachmann GR et al. 1993; Dotson MJ & Hyatt EV, 2005) for family activities such as choice of vacations and restaurants and consumer durables.

However, we find controversy through some researchers, Holdert and Antonides (as cited in Jones SC & Reid A, 2010) reported that children have more influence in the later stages of decision making: that is, at the time of evaluation of alternative, choice, and purchase for four purchases (holidays, adult and child clothing, and sandwich filling). Recently, Belch et al., (as cited in Bachmann GR et al. 1993) proposed that as teenagers more frequent users of the Internet, they have greater access and easy approach to market information and product information which could impact their influence in family decision making. They found that teens who perceive themselves to be ‘Internet mavens’ (individuals who are relied upon more for providing information from the virtual marketplace), as well as their parents, believed that teens were more influential in all stages-initiation and information search, and alternative evaluation and final decision stages. However, their influence was higher in the initiation and information search stages as compared to alternative evaluation and final decision stages.

Advertisers target at children because of their high pocket monies, their early recognition and loyalty to certain brands and a conventional wisdom that young adults buy products on impulse (Farooq AJ et al. 2010) Many parents and critics fear that children are easily deceptive by the commercials because the thing they lack is necessary cognitive skills to process highly persuasive message and consequently, they are not able to make appropriate judgments about them (Jozsa L, Eszter T & István S, 1980) There are educators and researchers who are have tried and keen to design programs that will make children able to about the intent of advertisements and also help children to construct defenses and arguments from commercial messages (Dotson MJ & Hyatt EV, 2005)

3. Research Design and Methodology

3.1 Study Variables

In order to determine the items that needed to be contained in the survey questionnaire, a preliminary consultation was conducted to identify the most important influencing factors that could influence the parent's buying decision to take on the child's behavior. This was done with 30 families who have children ages 6 to 12 years old in in Bandar Abbas, Islamic Republic of Iran where a

major question were asked of them: What factors have caused your buying decision to be influenced by your child's behavior or choice?

The study was able to identify the fifteen items in three categories as the most important factors which can influence the buying decisions of parents of children. The results of this preliminary consultation are presented hereunder which became the basis for designing the survey questionnaire and distributing it among respondents.

Table 1. Research Variables Category and its Components

Child's Individual Qualities	Gender
	Age
	Pocket Money
	Pester Power
Family Demographic Qualities	Household Size
	Income Level
	Culture
	Single Parent Households
	More Stress in Life
Learning History	Lesser Time with Family
	TV Advertising
	Internet Advertising
	Newspaper and Magazine Advertising
	Mobile Advertising
	Peer Group Effects

3.2. Population and Sample

Data were collected through a questionnaire that was implemented in person through interviews with 385 families randomly who have children ages 6 to 12 years old in Bandar Abbas, Islamic Republic of Iran. The sample was calculated according to the Cochran formula.

N = Statistical population size = 550,000

Z = Confidence Level= 95%

p = Ratio of a trait in the population = 50%

q = Percentage of those without that trait in the population ($q = 1-p$)

d = Acceptable margin of error = 5%

n = Sample size = 384

3.3 Methodology

In order to answer the questions of this study, the descriptive survey was considered adequate, as our goal was to identify and prioritize the factors that make parents' decisions overshadowed by their children, based on the results obtained using quantitative and qualitative methods. Keeping in mind that the project sought to evaluate a total of 15 variables, the sample was calculated according to Cochran formula. Seeking better coverage to define the issues which make up the research instrument, interviews were carried out using the focus group technique, based on the reflections expressed orally by the participants.

Collection and classification of the variables helped to define the issues that composed the research instrument which was created based on Guadalupe (2000) with closed questions on the Likert scale. To make the questionnaire more didactic and appropriate for the parents of children, an image of an increasing number of stars was used; in other words, no importance earned zero stars, and four stars marked maximum importance. The data was analyzed using a multivariate analysis to conduct a descriptive analysis tools such as Frequency-Means, Standard Deviation and Variance in order to verify the degree of importance of the variables.

4. Results

The variables found in the literature were qualitatively tested by a convenience sample which confirmed their own adequacy. The results of the quantitative survey show the priority and severity of effective factors, which ultimately compel parents to follow their children in making purchasing decisions of food products.

The most important identified variables to affect parental affiliation of children in the purchase decision are:

1. Gender (87.7%)
2. Age (86.1%)
3. Pester Power (85.5%)
4. TV Advertising (76.8%)
5. Peer Group Effects (75%)
6. Household Size (73.6%)
7. Lesser Time with Family (72.3%)
8. Income Level (65.1%)
9. Single Parent Households (63%)
10. More Stress in Life (45.6%)
11. Culture (32%)
12. Internet Advertising (30.3%)
13. Newspaper and Magazine Advertising (20%)
14. Pocket Money (12.7%)
15. Mobile Advertising (6.8%)

In contrast, in the assessment of the importance of the subject, the variables related to the child's individual qualities have the highest impact on the food products purchasing decision of parents. In this category of variables, the least important variable is "Pocket Money", reaching an average degree of importance of 2.08 in a range which varied from 1.20 to 2.50. The other variables which is considered to be of highest importance for these category is "Age", reaching an average degree of importance of 4.59, as can be seen in Table 1. This variable is known as the highest effective variable with the top score, compared to all the study variables.

In the second category, family demographic qualities can be mentioned. In this category of variables, the least important variable is family "Culture", reaching an average degree of importance of 2.43 in a range which varied from 1.50 to 3. The other variables which is considered to be of highest importance for these category is "Household Size", reaching an average degree of importance of 4.23, as can be seen in Table 1. It can be argued that smaller families are more dependent on their children in making purchasing decisions.

And finally, in the third category, learning history can be mentioned. In this category of variables, the least important variable is "Mobile Advertising ", reaching an average degree of importance of 1.98 in a range which varied from 1.20 to 2.25. This variable is known as the least effective variable with the lowest score, compared to all the study variables. The other variables which is considered to be of highest importance for these category is "TV Advertising ", reaching an average degree of importance of 4.49, as can be seen in Table 1. An implicit result that can be said on this subject is that advertising in the traditional media still have a greater impact on buying attitude, perspective and finally buying behavior of children in Bandar Abbas city (and perhaps in Iran) compared to modern advertising media such as the Internet and Mobile.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Table of the Research Variables Categories and its Components

Variables Category	Variables	N	Min	Max	Ave	SD
Child's Individual Qualities	Age	384	3.60	5	4.75	0.72
	Gender	384	3.80	5	4.59	0.88
	Pester Power	384	3.75	5	4.49	0.98
	Pocket Money	384	1.20	2.5	2.08	1.42
Family Demographic Qualities	Culture	384	1.50	3	2.43	1.19
	Household Size	384	3.60	5	4.23	1.15
	Income Level	384	3.50	5	3.98	1.12
	Lesser Time with Family	384	3.00	4.75	4.03	1.20
	More Stress in Life	384	3.25	4.5	3.63	1.36
	Single Parent Households	384	2.00	4.60	3.89	1.22
Learning History	Internet Advertising	384	1.45	3	2.40	1.30
	Mobile Advertising	384	1.20	2.25	1.98	0.93
	Newspaper & Magazine Advertising	384	1.50	2.5	2.11	1.19
	Peer Group Effects	384	3.75	5	4.46	1.20
	TV Advertising	384	3.50	5	4.49	0.98

5. Conclusion

We started with the aim to find out that is there any Influence of kids on purchasing decisions of food products in family and our findings provided astonishing insights for future researchers and marketing managers. We ended up with the findings that there is an important role of kids in purchasing decision of product in family, and they influence the purchasing decision. This is why, in societies like Iran, age and gender of children along with pester power are counted as the most important factor that leads parents to follow their children.

One of the most interesting findings of this research is that TV advertising is a fourth important factor. This shows that how much child's put their attention to television advertisement and they think it reliable enough to use it as a reference to pester their parents. Iranian children in Bandar Abbas city think that advertisements they see in television are quite influencing but simultaneously they perceive the brand as good or bad one by using and analyzing its quality. This result may be generalized to the all Iranian children. So, marketers must be consistent in what they show and actually provide to customers. Finally, according to research findings, we are suggesting future researchers to study why in Iranian society, modern advertising tools such as the Internet and mobile do not have a significant impact on purchasing decisions.

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